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THE INEQUALITY IN DIVIDING HOUSEHOLD CHORES IN WORKING MOTHER NOVELS

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Abstract: In many countries, the rate of women's participation in the working field keeps increasing from time to time because of the increase in their educational level and economic condition. This condition leads to some changes concerning the gender roles in a family, however, it does not change the division of household chores between husband and wife. Women are still considered as the main person to do most of the household chores. This topic is often presented as the main theme in some literary works, particularly novels. This research examines three different novels, *Opening Belle*, *I Don't Know How She Does It* and *The Balance Project*, by analyzing the inequality in dividing household chores faced by the working mothers in the novels. This research uses qualitative method consisting of description, reduction and selection stages. From the analysis results, it can be seen that the working mothers still do most of the household chores, while their husband does not help them much. Although they can pay someone to help them do the chores, however, the help is not as good as expected. They still have to struggle in combining between household chores and work which eventually makes them feel exhausted.

Keywords: household chores, inequality, working mother, novels

Introduction

In many countries, women's participation to work outside the house increases along with the increase of economic condition and educational levels. Women need to have the opportunity to work because working can help overcome gender disparities such as in terms of getting income and making decisions in the family. The increase in the number of working women has changed some of the social attitudes for women but not completely changed the roles of women at home. Women who work outside the home usually still have to play a role in managing home and family. Their husband may contribute to taking out the trash or tidying the lawn, but on average they spend less time doing this than women doing other household chores. This applies to women who work full

time and those who can pay someone to help out at home. If a woman can pay for help, in the end, she still needs to arrange how the workers clean the house or look after their children. She also still has to meet her children's needs including being involved in school activities.

Household chores consist of domestic chores, child care and kin work. The disparity in the division of household chores between a working mother and her partner is due to the patriarchal understanding that defines household chores as a woman's duty. This makes women have a double burden, namely at home and work, and they must be able to balance these two roles well. The theme of the inequality of the division of household chores is raised in various literary works, especially novels, so this research investigates the

conflict of inequality in the division of household chores in three novels with the theme of working mothers, namely *Opening Belle*, *I Don't Know How She Does It* and *The Balance Project*. The focus of the discussion, in general, is directed at the novel *Opening Belle* and *I Don't Know How She Does It* because the novel *The Balance Project* only discusses working mothers in general.

Gender inequality in household chores has become fruitful sources of study in the field of psychology as well as literature. The psychological study depicts the real-life involving the real investigation. Cerrato (2018) investigated gender inequality in household chores concerning the increase of Work-Family Conflict (WFC). The results showed that traditional gender role still affects the way men and women manage work and family interaction.

Syamsudin (2007) investigated feminism in American society. The time setting is in the industrial era at the end of the 19th century. The main resource or data is the novel *Main Street* written by Sinclair Lewis. The study revealed that at the end of the century, American women experienced discrimination and subordination. This novel promoted equality between men and women in social life.

The other prominent scholar, Van Hooff (2011) investigated the explanations and justifications offered by dual-career heterosexual couples in defence of an unequal division of housework within their relationship. The research findings revealed that a number of the couples employ similar justifications, with both male and female respondents arguing that women have higher standards and are more competent performers of household chores and that the definition of labour is practical, based on the hours worked by both partners.

Based on several studies above, the fact that the inequality of household chores between men and women still occurs. This phenomenon triggers the researchers to investigate this notion by focusing on several literary works in the form of novels. Novels can represent various things, including the writers' point of view on real life.

Method

This study employs a qualitative research method consisting of the description, reduction and selection stages. The research stage begins by observing the depiction of the characters and the problems raised in the novel, continues to reduce the information obtained from the description stage and focuses on the problems raised in the theme, then ends by connecting the data obtained with the theory used.

Findings and Discussion

The increase in the number of working women is an important indicator of economic growth. A record of this sharp increase occurred in the 20th century when the number of women participating in the labour market in the early-industrialized countries is shown in graph 1.0. This graph illustrates the level of participation of women who are economically active by combining data from countries that are members of the OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development). The graph depicts a positive trend in all countries, in particular, growth in participation, even though it started at different points in time, and continued at different rates; but the substantial and sustained increase in female labour force participation in wealthy countries remained a striking feature of the economic and social changes in the 20th century.

Figure 1.0. Long-Term Perspective of the Female Labor Participation Rate from 1890 to 2016. (<https://ourworldindata.org/female-labor-supply>)

Women's participation in the labour market has changed a lot in the last 50 years due to many factors such as the absence of

additional income, the husband's single income is no longer able to meet their needs, the growing desire of women to enter public life and to gain economic independence, and the availability of childcare services (Dex, 2003: 10). The involvement of women in economic matters encourages changes in traditional gender roles. The stereotype of women who have dominant roles in doing household chores now has to divide their roles with tasks in the workplace so they are prone to conflict. Therefore, she needs help from those around her so that she can carry out both roles well. Seccombe & Warner (2004: 431) divides household chores into three interrelated series of activities, namely domestic chores, child care and kin work. This study will discuss conflicts of inequality in the division of household chores by discussing three novels with the theme of working mothers, namely *Opening Belle* by Maureen Sherry, *The Balance Project* by Susie Orman Schnall and *I Don't Know How She Does It* by Allison Pearson. The novel *The Balance Project* with the main character Katherine only discusses working mothers in general so that there is not much data related to conflicts in the division of household chores, so the focus of the discussion of the theme is directed at two other novels with the main character named Isabelle McElroy or Belle in the novel *Opening Belle* and Katharine or Kate in the novel *I Don't Know How She Does It*.

As mentioned above, several factors cause women to participate in earning a living. Sometimes they are forced to become the breadwinner in their household. Maureen Sherry in her novel *Opening Belle* quotes a *New York Times* article writing that ... 40 per cent of American households with children now have women being the primary breadwinner ... (2016: 101). This condition is experienced by the main character in this novel named Isabelle McElroy. This is not much different from Katherine's character in the novel *I Don't Know How She Does It*. The husbands of these two figures have jobs that are not permanent so they have to fulfil their family needs. However, the increase of their participation in work has not changed the traditional gender roles that have been adopted by patriarchy too much. Domestic roles attached to women often place women working in conflict because on the one hand,

she has to be fully responsible for domestic chores, while on the other hand she has responsibilities outside her home, namely work. Significant differences in the distribution of domestic work continue when the wife works outside the home. Winqvist's (2004: 44) research shows that women in Europe spend between 60 and 70 per cent of their time doing household chores, while men spend 35 to 45 per cent. This condition is almost the same as what happens in America, such as when the character Katherine in the novel *The Balance Project*, who works as a writer, is interviewed by a journalist who asks why the balance between work and household chores is still a hot issue. Kate said, "Well, women make up approximately 60 per cent of the American workforce, yet they spend twice as many hours as men on childcare and housework." (Schnall, 2015: 6-7).

This imbalance in the division of household chores is due to the patriarchal notion that refers to the dominance of men over power relations where men dominate women, and to define a system in which women are always placed lower in various ways (Bachsin, 2006: 3). Millet (1977: 35) adds that this male domination is carried out through various institutions such as high schools, churches and families, each of which justifies and strengthens the position of men over women. The novel *I Don't Know How She Does It* shows this domination through religion when Kate opens a book entitled *Saying of the World's Great Religion* which says that the wife is 'home' thus affirming the notion of domestication of women. Another way to confirm the patriarchy is through the lyrics of children song. Kate sings a lullaby about it for Ben saying "Lavender blue dilly, dilly, lavender's green. When I am King dilly, dilly. Ou shall be Queen." (Pearson, 2002: 75). This song has been sung through generations without knowing the exact meaning. For Kate, the purpose of the song is to make a woman or for this term is Queen to follow the instinct of a woman to serve the King, or the man.

The concept of patriarchy also causes a different opinion about the good mother and bad mother. Because patriarchy puts women to be at the domestic sphere, therefore housewives are better than the working mothers. Among women, it often causes them to have some arguments. Kate itself is often

asked by her neighbour who is a housewife whether she has quit from working full time or not. In Kate's opinion, all mothers have their anxiety, they feel jealous of each other.

I suspect that the nonworking mother looks at the working mother with envy and fear because she thinks that the working mum has got away with it, and the working mum looks back with fear and envy because she knows she has not. In order to keep going in either role, you have to convince that the alternative is bad (Pearson, 2002: 96)

This causes Kate to feel guilty that she does not stay home often to take care of the house and her family. Patriarchy causes Kate's husband not to feel the way Kate feels when he has to work outside the home because this understanding says that the role of men is in the public sphere ... no man has ever had to ask for advice on how to combine fatherhood and a career (Pearson, 2002: 228). The privilege of this male role causes them not to be much involved in activities related to household chores so that if they are involved in it, they feel proud and can show it off to those around them. Both *Opening Belle* and *I Don't Know How She Does It* show the readers how fathers display photos of their children on their desks to show that they can still make time for them amid their busy life, while women will feel guilty if they do the same thing because she will be seen as thinking more about her family than her job. Belle's character says, "Men have no problem impressing their bosses with their family-man rap; while women never dare mention their families at work," (Sherry, 2016: 85). In line with this, the character Kate says if a man puts a photo of his child on the table, it shows that he is a good head of the family, while if this is done by a woman, the impression will be the opposite. This is because a man's nature is not in his house with his children; it is women who have this responsibility.

Domestication is a part of feminine mystique described by feminist figure Betty Friedan in her book entitled *Feminine Mystique*. In this book, she defines what is currently referred to as the stereotype of ideal women as those who find feminine fulfilment

when she focuses only on her husband, her children and her home (Friedan, 1963: 18). Friedan writes that women like this spend too much time cleaning houses, enhancing their already attractive appearance and spoiling their children. She concludes that women need to find income-generating jobs in the public sector. Working outside the home for women can fulfil their social obligations and make women free to fill their roles and responsibilities in the public sphere.

Conflict of Inequality in Dividing Household Chores in Novel *I Don't Know How She Does It*

The novel *I Don't Know How She Does It* tells about the character of Katherine or often called Kate, a successful career woman who works at a leading financial company, *Edwin Morgan Forster*, as the youngest senior director. She is 35 years old and has two children, Emily and Ben. Her husband, Richard, works at a housing agency whose job is temporary. Under the title of this novel, Kate's daily life is filled with considerations of who needs her attention the most; whether children, work or her husband. Although Richard stays at home more often because he does not always get a job, Kate still has to do various household chores. The task of cooking, for example, is still the responsibility of Kate even though at that time she comes home from work late at night. She feels responsible to do this because she reads a letter from Emily's school asking Emily to bring snacks in celebration of a Christmas party at school. Kate concludes that every letter from school addressed to parents, is meant to be addressed to the mother ... (Has a father who has a wife on the premises ever read a note from school?) (Pearson, 2002: 4). Kate is willing to do this because she remembers that when she was a child, her friend who brought food from the store at the Harvest Festival at the church was thought to have a mother who did not pay attention to her child because she was busily working. She does not want Emily to get the same treatment that can cause Emily to feel sad and then impacts her psychological condition when she grows up.

Apart from cooking, the household chores that Kate has to do was cleaning the house which she does after she finishes

cooking snacks for Emily. She sees that the kitchen is messy; toys are scattered all over the place, a pile of raisins that has been there since morning, rotten fruit still on the dining table, and dirty napkins that no one else has thought to throw away. Richard, her husband, asks her to rest because it is already late at night, but Kate cannot. Richard does not help Kate much with cleaning the house. Kate repeatedly reminds Richard to clean the house but Richard often ignores Kate's requests

11.19 P.M. Arrive home to discover the Pocket Memory Connect Kit on the hall table. Richard is shipwrecked on the sofa watching the Arsenal Game. He has left some pasta in the oven; it has the texture and smell of baked toes.

“Would it be totally out of question for anyone except me to take stuff left at the bottom of the stairs upstairs?” (Pearson, 2002: 142)

The chores of cleaning the house are seen as a woman's destiny to do it, as depicted in Kate's mother character, whose mother has never been seated as long as Kate can remember. She always stood behind the sink, behind the ironing board, carries the dish of food from the kitchen and after that takes it all back. Her mother's generation was born to provide services so that she would lose direction if this was taken from her. When Kate was a teenager, she thought that even though men seemed to play an important role in the world, it was women who made men able to appear in public well ... It was a matriarchy pretending to be patriarchy to keep the lads happy (Pearson, 2002: 281). This view is also shared by Kate's mother-in-law, Barbara. In Barbara's life, husbands are not involved in household chores at all. Barbara treats her husband like a farm animal that needs special care, so she would blame Kate if Richard looks thin. To ease the responsibilities of doing domestic chores, Kate hires Juanita to clean her house. But the help she expects from Juanita is difficult to fulfil because Juanita often complains about pain in various parts of her body so that she is unable to clean the house thoroughly. As a result, Kate still has to do domestic chores after work or on holidays. Besides that, Rich also does not want to be asked to buy groceries when the

name is related to women. For example when Kate asks Rich to buy kitchen roll named Kitten Soft three times, however, Rich can not find it in the store but he can not ask the shop assistant because the name of the kitchen roll seems feminine. He tells Kate that as a man, he can say some words like Toilet-Duck, Glade-fresh, rich aroma, deep-dish, fillet o'fish, Cheezy Dipper, wash'n'go, Bodyform, Tubby Custard, panty liner (Pearson, 2002:107)

Apart from domestic chores, inequality in the division of household chores is also evident in terms of childcare. To help her take care of her children while she is working, Kate hires a nanny named Paula who is often late. Kate can go to work when Paula arrives, while Richard can leave without thinking about it... Richard has to leave early: a site visit with a client in Battersea. Can I do the handover with Paula? (Pearson, 2002: 13). Paula's late arrival also results in Kate being late to the office. In order not to be judged badly by his superiors, she has to give reasons for being late on what is called as male reasons, such as traffic jams on the road. If she gives the reason for the delay because she has to take care of her children first, she will be considered as an employee who does not put the interests of the company first. But on the other hand, society still demands a mother as the party who has the most responsibility for ensuring the welfare of her children. Paula is the person Kate counts on when she's not at home. Problems will arise when Paula cannot come to Kate's house because she is sick. This situation causes Kate to find a way out before she can go to work while Richard has gone on a project presentation. Kate, who is scheduled to chair an important meeting that day, decides to leave Ben and Emily with her neighbours for a while. A mother is also required to be able to deal with her sick child. Ten-month-old Ben is in a teething period which makes him cry a lot at night. An exhausted Kate wakes up when she hears Ben's screams, while Richard is still fast asleep. Ben accidentally bites Kate's neck leaving a red mark and his office friends asked about the wound.

“Hey, did Slow Richard give you a hickey? That's terrific honey.”

“No, the teething baby did. My darling husband slept through all. But I nearly

bit him to wake him up (Pearson, 2002: 78)

Child welfare also involves parents' participation in the education of their children. Emily's friends' mothers expect Kate to attend a meeting between parents and teachers holding before Kate comes home from work. As a result, three months after joining, Kate never attends a single meeting. Since the beginning, Kate's goal in joining this organization is to take part in Emily's education like the mothers of Emily's friends, most of whom work as housewives. ... I was thinking that just for one hour in some underlit overheated classroom, I could pretend that I'm like any other mother (Pearson, 2002: 214). Alexandra Law, the head of this organization, often insinuates that Kate is still working full time so that she doesn't have much role in school activities. Another activity at Emily's school that Kate wants to attend is a Christmas play she can hardly attend because she has a sudden task from her boss. She finally arrives late which is indicated by the sound of his shoes on Emily's school floor which seems to be made to expose a working mother who is late arriving. Kate is eager to attend the show because last year she couldn't come because she had to catch a flight to America. The times she cannot come are the times the kids will remember, not the other way around.

The third type of household chores are duties towards relatives or often called as kin work. Amid her busy schedule, Kate still has to think about the Christmas gifts she should bring to celebrate at her mother-in-law's house. The process of giving gifts starting from buying wrapping paper, buying gifts, giving words in it until sending it through the post office is entirely done by Kate. One tradition is that I buy all the presents for my side of the family [] and presents for Richard's parents (Pearson, 2002: 42-43). But when they are at Richard's parents' house, Richard's father and mother will rather thank Richard for bringing them gifts and wine. Kate feels disrespected for her efforts.

To make up for her guilt because she cannot involve a lot in her children's development, Kate buys various items to please her children. Currently, Emily has a variety of toys that mark Kate's guilt. Kate's

guilt arises even when Emily wasn't born. Kate is the first woman to become pregnant at Edwin Morgan Forster. When she is six-month pregnant, she is told by her boss who says the company can not guarantee that they still have work for Kate once Kate returns from maternity leave. This company has a friendly policy towards married employees, but because policies such as maternity leave have never been used by men, women should also not use them since they do not want to be considered not seriously working. As a result, Kate tries to work harder so as not to lose her job. Entering 32 weeks of pregnancy, Kate is told by her obstetrician that Kate is too stressed which endangers her baby's brain development. Kate's guilt leads her to choose to give birth normally without the aid of an epidural so she can prove to her baby that she is still able to endure pain for her baby's safety.

Conflict of Inequality of Household Chores in *Opening Belle*

The second novel to be discussed in this study is entitled *Opening Belle* by Maureen Sherry. The main character in this novel is a working mother named Isabelle McElroy in her 30s. She is married to Bruce Cassidy and has three children. Isabelle or Belle works as an executive manager at a stock company called *Feagin Dixon* located on the Wall Street complex. Belle's husband, Bruce, does not have a steady job and is at home more often than Belle. One of Belle's domestic chores is shopping for her daily needs. Her husband, Bruce, does not care if the refrigerator is empty so Belle has to be responsible for buying groceries. Having three young children means that Isabelle and Bruce's house never looks clean. Isabelle's full-time job keeps her from tidying up her house often so she hires a household assistant to help her. But the household assistant has often come home when the house is still in a mess and Bruce does not want to clean it up. They leave it just like that because they already gets used to it and Belle will take care of it in the end. One day Kate is angry about this and said.

"It says nobody cares at all. It says let all this shit hang out till Mom comes home because she'll fix everything. She'll earn the money! She'll order all

the groceries and arrange for cleaning and cooking..." (Sherry, 2016:268-267).

In terms of childcare, Belle also plays a more dominant role than her husband, even though her husband is with them more often. Belle's friend said, "I think you're still doing most of the kid work even though he's home most of the time." (Sherry, 2016: 214). Although Belle often has to make official trips abroad for her work, she still has to make arrangements at home so that all activities can run smoothly, for example whether Kevin, her eldest son, has been picked up after playing with friends; what her household assistant cooks for dinner and whether Owen, her youngest son, can take a good nap. Belle is also responsible for choosing the clothes the children will wear tomorrow because when this responsibility is given to Bruce, he cannot choose an appropriate outfit. The task is taken over by Belle because Brigid's teacher tells her that Brigid goes to school without wearing any underwear. Belle often covers up the condition of her family by saying that Bruce involves a lot in taking care of the children so that her husband will not continue to be blamed for not working. "Bruce helps a lot with the kids." I lied (Sherry, 2016: 17). When in fact what Bruce does more often is to have fun with the money made by Belle. Bruce is too lazy to find work because he can rely on his wife's income. Bruce's immaturity is also seen when Belle decides to be a host in a meeting with other working mothers who have toddlers. Belle decides to join this playgroup meeting because she wants to be more involved in her children's activities. Belle is almost late to arrive home because she is suddenly asked to give a presentation. When she gets home she finds that her babysitter is angry because she has to watch over all the toddlers who are there, while Bruce is busy drinking wine with Belle's guests.

Like Kate, responsibility towards relatives is also Belle's responsibility, for example, when she has to buy Christmas gifts for her family. Belle buys these gifts before she attends the office party before the Christmas holidays. Belle feels embarrassed to bring this bag of toys to a party in her office because everyone looks elegant without carrying a big

bag of toys like her. This bag makes her look so motherly that she wants to hide behind her friend Marcus... Hide me Marcus. I look like a mother, for God's sake ... (Sherry, 2016: 5). The toys that Belle has bought sounds many times when Belle stumbles on something. This attracts the attention of her friends who are motivated to play them until that one of the children's toys is broken.

Being busily working makes Belle feel guilty for leaving her children too often. She feels she has lost a lot of time with them. Time passed makes Belle realize that her children grow up. In fact, the time given to parents to raise their children is not as long as one might think because they are growing rapidly... Most things aren't there for us as long as we think that they will be (Sherry, 2016: 106). But for now, Belle cannot decide to stop working because her family still needs income from her. Although for Belle's friends, combining a work-life with a family of three children is not possible.

The Consequences of Inequality in Dividing Household Chores for Working Mothers

The existence of this inequality in dividing household chores makes Kate and Belle exhausted. Kate asks her husband, Rich, to support her by helping her in all matters relating to the family as she is also tired of the unfair treatment she receives in the office just because she is a working mother. Belle also feels the same way. Her workmates often doubt her ability to get the job done because she has too many things to handle. She feels able to handle everything even though she also feels that she has too much responsibility.... I'm fully capable of taking care of Bruce and our brood; it's just so much responsibility. It's so lonely. (Sherry, 2016: 112).

Basically, the two main figures depicted in the novels love their work. They see work as a good thing to do since they can refresh from the chaotic condition at home. Kate loves her job because she likes the synapse-snapping satisfaction of being good at it, of being control when the rest of life seems such an awful mess (Pearson, 2002: 16). However, this feeling also causes her to feel guilty because of the less involvement of her roles at home. One day she has a nightmare about leaving her family late at night because

she has to do something at the office, then finds her home in a fire after coming back. This nightmare makes her afraid that this will become real while she is at work. Similar guilty feeling is also experienced by Belle when she has to go abroad for a business trip. Her family is fine when she leaves home to work. Some things may be a little bit messy, but generally, everything can run smoothly. It makes her think whether her family needs her or not...My family needs me. They need you?...(Sherry, 2016:23)

To balance roles at home and work, a working mother must be able to do many things at one time or it is called multitasking. Kate tells her husband that she should be able to remember everything, while it will be impossible to ask Rich to remember three things at the same time. Besides, a working mother must also be seen to be able to separate the two roles. When she is at home she must act as a mother, while when she is at the office, she must act as a good employee. Belle called this separation the mental term of filing cabinet. Each piece is placed in a separate container and ensure that no leaks occur. This is often difficult to do, but not impossible.

“She jams a family problem into a mental filing cabinet, slams the door shut, and does her work. When she gets home she reverses the process, disconnecting her wireless world while reviewing first-grade spelling words..”(Sherry, 2016: 65)

However, this method is not always successful. Belle and Kate can do it for a while, but Kate eventually stops working because she continues to feel guilty about leaving her growing children. Kate does not feel like losing her growing children. On the other hand, Belle is still working until the end of the story. She quits from Feagin Dixon and then starts her own company.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis of the discussion on the theme of conflict inequality in the division of household chores from three novels on the theme of working mothers, it can be revealed that the characters Isabelle and Katharine

experience this inequality. They still do most of the household chores even though their husbands are more often at home because they do not have permanent jobs. To reduce this burden, they hired people to help him, but their assistance was not what was expected. The cause of this inequality in the division of household chores is the patriarchy that places women at home, looking after their homes and families. Although nowadays many women work outside the home, this understanding is still being applied so that it makes working mothers have a dual role, namely at home and at work.

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